

Cover

ANTI-SUPERBUGS PCP **Fighting Multi-Drug Resistant Organisms** **in hospitals through Pre-commercial** **Procurement.**

<p><i>When citing, sharing, or adapting this work, please provide proper attribution as follows:</i></p>	<p>Jean-Patrick Mathieu, Esther Arévalo</p> <p>AQuAS - Agency for Health Quality and Assessment of Catalonia (Spain)</p>
<p>Abstract</p>	<p>ANTI-SUPERBUGS PCP aims to improve the quality of care processes in hospitals and to reduce both the costs and the collateral effects caused by Multi-Drug Resistant Organisms (MDROs, aka “Superbugs”) and other Health Associated Infections’ pathogens. This is to be achieved through the development and testing of prototype devices and ICT services that can: 1) non-invasively test for the presence of MDROs and other pathogens, and 2) provide continuous information and remote alerts to health professionals on contamination by pathogens on high contact surfaces, applicable to existing healthcare environments.</p> <p>The project, co-funded by the EU H2020 Programme, is coordinated by AQuAS, which also acts as the lead procurer. It currently involves 4 procuring entities (Institut Catala d’Oncologia; Universitaetsklinikum Aachen; Sheffield Teaching Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust and Provincia Autonoma di Trento) plus partners with relevant expertise in public procurement (Sara Bedin) and technology (RISE).</p> <p>MDROs infections impact significant on morbidity, mortality and increased hospitalisation and costs, which adversely affect patient experience. MDROs are invisible to the naked eye and can survive on surfaces for many days, being transferred via human contact (patients, staff) or surfac contact. It is imperative to provide detection systems that can be easily integrated into healthcare facilities, enabling the control of MDROs.</p> <p>An open PCP will allow R&D service contracts to be awarded to a number of providers, in parallel, in a three-phase approach - 1) Solution design; 2) Prototyping; and 3) Original development and validation & testing. A Prior Information Notice will be published shortly in the OJEU, including information on an Open Market Consultation procedure.</p>

ANTI-SUPERBUGS PCP

Fighting Multi-Drug Resistant Organisms in hospitals through Pre-commercial Procurement.

Jean-Patrick Mathieu, Esther Arévalo, AQuAS - Agency for Health Quality and Assessment of Catalonia (Spain)

ANTI-SUPERBUGS PCP aims to improve the quality of care processes in hospitals and to reduce both the costs and the collateral effects caused by Multi-Drug Resistant Organisms (MDROs, aka "Superbugs") and other Health Associated Infections' pathogens. This is to be achieved through the development and testing of prototype devices and ICT services that can: 1) non-invasively test for the presence of MDROs and other pathogens, and 2) provide continuous information and remote alerts to health professionals on contamination by pathogens on high contact surfaces, applicable to existing healthcare environments.

The project, co-funded by the EU H2020 Programme, is coordinated by AQuAS, which also acts as the lead procurer. It currently involves 4 procuring entities (Institut Catala d'Oncologia; Universitaetsklinikum Aachen; Sheffield Teaching Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust and Provincia Autonoma di Trento) plus partners with relevant expertise in public procurement (Sara Bedin) and technology (RISE).

MDROs infections impact significant on morbidity, mortality and increased hospitalisation and costs, which adversely affect patient experience. MDROs are invisible to the naked eye and can survive on surfaces for many days, being transferred via human contact (patients, staff) or surface contact. It is imperative to provide detection systems that can be easily integrated into healthcare facilities, enabling the control of MDROs.

AT A GLANCE

Programme:	Horizont 2020
Duration:	01.09.2016 – 30.08.2020
Main outcome:	PCP for the development of early-and continuous-detection systems of microorganisms in hospitals and healthcare facilities
Website:	www.antisuperbugs.eu

An open PCP will allow R&D service contracts to be awarded to a number of providers, in parallel, in a three-phase approach - 1) Solution design; 2) Prototyping; and 3) Original development and validation & testing. A Prior Information Notice will be published shortly in the OJEU, including information on an Open Market Consultation procedure.

SMART@FIRE

Smart protection for firefighters all over Europe

Dorisz Tálás, INNOVA Észak-Alföld Nonprofit Kft. (Hungary)

The main objective of the Smart@fire project was to develop a smart Personal Protective System (PSS) for individual firefighters comprising of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) for clothing and a loosely connected ICT system. The ICT system integrates safety critical functions of the personal protection system of individual firefighters, and acts as a communication node for additional personal protection equipment as well as an interface to the local command centre. The system must be compliant with and fitted into the firefighter's clothing.

During the needs analysis it became clear that European countries can work together effectively on ICT developments in different areas. In the case of Smart@fire, despite the different levels of technology, the main aim was the same in all countries: to ensure safe working conditions for firefighters. The result of the Smart@fire project was very satisfactory, as development occurred which fulfilled all the necessary criteria and that proved its effectiveness during testing.

AT A GLANCE

Programme:	Seventh Framework Programme - FP7
Duration:	15.11.2012 – 15.02.2017
Main outcome:	PCP for developing innovative protective suit for firefighters
Website:	www.smartatfire.eu

The developed and tested Good PRO FR3 Fire Shark in smart its version is a certified three-layer protective suit for firefighters, which is designed mainly for extinguishing interior fires under extreme conditions in terms of temperature, fumes, and/or orientation in space. The system can continually monitor and evaluate the safety of the environment in which a firefighter is operating (temperature inside and outside the garment, moisture, humidity, toxic gases), and it also provides information about the position of the body, physiological functions as well as the firefighter's geographic location.

